

AIDAinnova

Advancement and Innovation for Detectors at Accelerators
Horizon 2020 Research Infrastructures project AIDAINNOVA

DELIVERABLE REPORT

PRESENTATION VIDEO

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Abstract:

This document details the presentation video that was produced to help deliver the projects' key messages and raise the interest of the public and other non-technical audiences in detector science. It also highlights the project's potential for science, industry and society.

AIDAinnova Consortium, 2022

For more information on AIDAinnova, its partners and contributors please see <http://aidainnova.web.cern.ch/>

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Delivery Slip

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

A short presentation video introduces the AIDAInnova project, its background and goals. The main focus is on the key challenges behind detectors technologies and on demonstrating the passion of scientists and engineers working on the project.

The two prime target groups are policymakers and industry, two audiences characterised respectively by their very limited technical knowledge or very specific knowledge. The secondary audiences are the general public and the internal one.

In August 2021, Design & Data GmbH was procured to create this video. In early-February 2022, a four-minute video was published. It combines already-existing footage from most beneficiaries with new, original ones, together with stock images enabling the representation of the widest range of applications of detector technologies. Three project members give a voice-over.

The video will be published on CERN official repository to archive and disseminate videos (CDS Video), the Organization's YouTube channel and published on social media. It will also be used by the other partners and included in publications (On Track newsletter) and presentations.

The video is available here: <https://videos.cern.ch/record/2295524>

1. INTRODUCTION

The communication plan for AIDAinnova is based on experience with communicating similar H2020 projects (e.g. AIDA-2020), on the best practices of CERN and DESY in communication and outreach in multi-stakeholder scenarios.

The main communication goals for AIDAinnova are:

1. Implement effective knowledge sharing among the project participants.
2. Engage the wider detector community with the project developments.
3. Facilitate the knowledge transfer between academia and industry.
4. Engage the public with detector science and its applications.
5. Demonstrate the project is on track and its objectives are being achieved.
6. Demonstrate the impact of the project to the public and policy makers.

These goals define the project's audiences: participants, early-career researchers, the detector community, wider scientific community, industry, policy-makers, funding agencies, and the general public. According to their potential for engagement, the project's communication team will use appropriate channels and activities, and it will endeavour to create content that is fit for a multi-channel, multi-stakeholder approach, i.e. providing several levels of engagement for different audiences.

In order to provide the project with a communication tool that could be used throughout its duration and in multiple channels, it was decided at the start of the project to create a **presentation video**:

“A presentation video will be produced to help deliver the projects' key messages and raise the interest of the public and other non-technical audiences in detector science. It will include its potential for science, industry and society. It should build up on the achievements of previous projects, such as AIDA and AIDA-2020, and highlight the expected outcome of AIDAinnova”.

AIDAinnova DoA, 2020, page 23.

This deliverable report details goals, audiences, channels, and evaluation metrics for the project's communication. It also describes the communication material for industry and other audience, as well as the social media strategy of the project.

2. STRATEGY

2.1. OBJECTIVES OF THE VIDEO

The objectives of the video are the following:

- Introduce the project.
- Expose the main challenges behind detectors technologies as well its outcome: a better understanding of our Universe and a contribution to society.
- Show the fascination behind the endeavour of technology development, and to demonstrate the passion of scientists and engineers working on the project.

2.2. MESSAGES

The core messages of the video are the following:

- Europe has taken a leading role in the particle physics international community and AIDAInnova is also part of that.
- Demonstrate the challenges of detector development: speed, cooling, radiation tolerance, etc.
- Demonstrate what the detectors do. (Representation through Onion metaphor showing the differing layers of the detectors in terms of elements and technologies).
- Demonstrate what we have gained with applying detectors in other areas of society: medicine, aerospace, cultural restoration, environment, etc.
- Demonstrate the diversity of AIDAInnova:
 - AIDAInnova gathers a community of over 30 partners from all over Europe. It is not just about big institutes like CERN but also national ones.
 - AIDAInnova gathers not only physicists but also engineers, system designers, technical specialists that work in the community.
- Inspire next generations by highlighting the education aspect of the project.

2.3. TARGETS

Audience	Outcome	Drivers (characteristics)
Main targets		
Funding agencies & decision-makers	Support to funding for fundamental research; support to project community	Scientific excellence; economic and societal impact (Very limited technical knowledge)
Industry	Co-innovations; knowledge and technology transfer, collaborations	Innovation; job creation; collaboration (Very specific knowledge and no knowledge over the bigger picture)
Secondary targets		
Public	Support for fundamental research; attracting young generations to science careers	Curiosity, societal impact
Project participants & admin	Engagement with project results; sense of pride	Community spirit; career development

2.4. CHARACTERISTICS OF THE VIDEO

This four-minute video gives an overview of the challenges of particle detectors while introducing the AIDAinnova project.

Special attention was given in representing the diversity of backgrounds, nationalities and institutes, three project members were given the possibility to narrate the video. In the same spirit, the video combines already-existing footage from most beneficiaries (CERN, DESY, INFN) with new, original ones from smaller institutes. It also uses archive footage coming from AIDA-2020. Finally, stock footage was used to show the widest range of applications of detector technologies. The editing follows the corporate colours and identity.

It was decided to go with a jargon-free, accessible style and avoid acronyms. Inspirational and casual, special emphasis was given in the script to share the wonder and curiosity that drives the development of these systems.

A standalone piece will be done with extracts of the video to focus on societal applications for detectors.

2.5. TIMELINE

The production of the video suffered from delay caused by the early replacement of the communication officer of the project at the start of procurement, CERN procurement rules, lack of “complete offers”, holiday season and difficulties in getting time-slots for interviews and shooting.

2.6. USAGE OF THE VIDEO

The video has been published on CERN official repository to archive and disseminate videos (CDS Video), the Organization’s YouTube channel and published on social media. It will also be used by the other partners and included in publications (*On Track* newsletter) and presentations.

The video is available here:

- <https://videos.cern.ch/record/2295524>
- <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=E3IQbVLrF5U>

3. FUTURE PLANS

This video makes the choice of using its partners social media channels to communicate its news. If successful, this strategy will be recommended and/or applied to other EU projects coordinated by CERN, on the basis of the network established for AIDAinnova.